

Studies on the Murexide Complex of Vanadium in Glycine Buffer*

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Murexide has largely been used for the colorimetric estimation of alkaline earth metals^{1,2}, Cu(II) and Zn(II)^{3,4}. The color reactions of some rare earth metals like scandium, thorium and zirconium with the help of this compound are also reported⁵ in the literature. Systematic and comprehensive studies on murexide complexes have, however, not been undertaken so far. Investigations in this direction were therefore undertaken. The present communication deals with the composition of murexide complex of Vo^{+2} . Preliminary experiments have shown that vanadyl sulfate reacts with murexide to give a violet coloured compound in glycine buffer of pH 6.2 to 7.2. The colour changes of murexide from red to violet or orange is a clear indication of complex formation⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents and solutions : Vanadyl sulfate murexide, glycine sodium, chloride were analar grade (B.D.H.) reagents. The solutions were made in double distilled water. The strength of vanadyl sulfate was determined volumetrically⁷.

Apparatus : Optical density measurements were carried out with a Bausch and Lomb 'Spectronic 20'. pH measurements were made with 'Cambridge Bench pH-meter' with a glass electrode which had been cleaned thoroughly with dilute acid. The pH-meter was standardized using a buffer of potassium hydrogen phthalate of pH-4.

Amperometric titrations were carried out with the help of Toshniwal manual polarograph type Cl. 0-2 using Pye scalamp galvanometer in the external circuit. Purified hydrogen was used for the deaeration. A Fisher capillary with a drop time of 3-4 secs. (open circuit) was used for d.m.c. The capillary constant $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$, was 1.877. Sodium chloride was used as the supporting electrolyte.

Procedure : Vosburgh and Copper's method⁸ was employed to know the number of complexes formed by the interaction of vanadium with murexide. The composition of the

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1. Max. B. Willians and James H. Moser, *Anal. Chim.*, 1953, **25**, 1414.
2. E. M. Yakimets and N. M. Chernovima Trudy. *Anal. Politekh Inst.*, 1956, No. 57, 106; *Referat. Zhur. Met.*, 1957, Abs. No. 7097.
3. V. N. Tolmachev and O. M. Kirzhnev, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1958, **13**, 430.
4. G. A. Panosyan, *Izrest. Akad. Nauk. Armyan*, S.S.R. Biol. Nauki, 1958, **12**, No. 8, 15.
5. G. Beck, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1947, **1**, 69, in German.
6. Chemistry of the metal chelate compounds by Martell and Calvin, p. 485 (1962).
7. Scotts Standard methods of Chemical Analysis, by N. H. Furman, Vol. 1, p. 254.
8. Vosburgh, W. C. and Copper, G. R., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.

interaction product was determined by applying the Job's method of continuous variation⁹ and molar ratio method¹⁰. For Job's method, equimolar solutions of vanadyl sulfate and murexide of concentration $0.001M$, $0.002M$ were mixed according to the method of continuous variation. The differences of optical density of the mixtures and vanadyl sulfate was plotted against the ratio metal/metal+murexide. The results are shown in Fig. 1. The stability constant of the complex was calculated from the data of Job's method.

In order to verify whether hydrogen ions were liberated during complex ion formation, pH -metric titrations of the mixture of vanadyl sulfate and murexide in the ratio 1 : 0, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 against ($0.1M$) KOH were carried out. A downward shift in pH in the order 1 : 0, 1 : 1 was observed (Fig. 2). Blank experiments were performed separately with murexide and caustic potash solutions. The curves obtained therein did not interfere with the titration curves described above.

The stability of the complex was determined by Bjerrum's method (Fig. 3, 4). 20 ml. ($0.002M$) murexide with and without 5 ml., $0.002M$ vanadyl sulphate was titrated against

$0.02M$ KOH. The values of $\bar{n}$ average number of ligand bound per metal ion was evaluated and then plotted against the corresponding values of $-\log A$. The value of $-\log A$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ was taken as value of $\log K$.

9. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, (10), 113.

10. Instrumental Analysis by Clifton E. Melon and Robert W. Kiser, p. 8.

Amperometric titrations (Fig. 5) were carried out at the plateau of vanadyl sulphate in glycine buffer (-1.4 volts).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Vosburgh and Copper's method had shown the existence of one complex. The maximum obtained was found to be $480\text{ m}\mu$. The combining ratio of the complex was determined by spectrophotometric methods, and it was found to be 1 : 1. The results are in agreement with those obtained by *pH*-metric and amperometric methods.

The stability constant of the complex was determined from the data of Job's method applying the formula,

$$k = \frac{x}{(a_1 - x)(b_1 - x)} = \frac{x}{(a_2 - x)(b_2 - x)}$$

where a_1 and a_2 are the concentrations of metal, b_1 and b_2 are the concentrations of the murexide at different dilutions.

Stability constant of the complex by Job's method is 1.5×10^5 and this was further confirmed by Bjerrum's method. The value of (A^-) was calculated from the following equation,

$$TA = HA + A^- + MA^{n-1}$$

$$TM = M^n + MA^{n-1}$$

$$HA + A^- = TA - MA^{n-1}$$

$$A^- + \frac{(H)(A)}{K^z} = TA - MA^{n-1}$$

$$A^- = \frac{TA - MA^{n-1}}{1 + H/K^z}$$

11. Chemistry of metal chelate compounds by Martell and Calvin, p. 79, (1962).
12. Chemistry of metal chelate compounds by Martell and Calvin, p. 485, (1962).

where TA = total concentration of the ligand.
 TM = total concentration of the metal.
 n = valency of the metal ion.
 K = dissociation constant of the murexide.

The values of $\bar{n}$ were determined by

$$\bar{n} = \frac{TA - (A)}{TM}$$

Values of $\bar{n}$ obtained from this equation for each corresponding value of A were then plotted against $-\log A$. Typical curves are shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

Value of K was found to be 1.7×10^5 .

Schwarzenbach described the following form of both the dye and dye chelate in aqueous solution. The equilibria for these species are,

where H_4F^- represent the dye molecule with its four imido hydrogens but without the hydrogen which is replaced by the metal. Hence stoichiometric ratio obtained by the spectrophotometric and pH -metric methods may be represented on the basis of the above scheme by the following equation,

where n is the charge on the metal ion.

The complex could not be isolated in the solid state and further structural studies on them were not carried out.

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